

The Reduced Attention Span and Concentration Problems of Learners in Language Learning Classes.

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***Annotation.** This article describes the current problems occurring in learners of language classes including attention span reduction and issues with construction; the causes and potential solutions will be discussed.*

***Keywords:** concentration, digital distractions, brain activeness, mindfulness classes, impulsive behavior*

Introduction

Concentration is one of the most essential paths to a learner achievement and cognitive development. Due to accelerations and the advancements in technologies, attention spans of learners are dwindling and distractions are being increasingly prevalent. This is leading to the rise of concentration problems in learners that are affecting their academic performance and overall well-being. The purpose of this paper is to explore the causes, impacts and suggest creative as well as innovative solutions to address these issues.

Problem Overview

Many students struggle with lacking of attention and concentration at some point during their school years. Factors can be various, including digital distractions such as social media, mental health problems or hyper activity.

So, what is concentration?

We know that concentration is the ability to keep or maintain one's focus on completing one particular task. In scientific contexts, it has different meanings; in chemistry, concentration refers to the amount of a substance - solute, dissolved in a specific volume of solution (Brown et al., 2017). In psychological context, concentration means the process of cognitively focusing attention on a task while ignoring internal and external distractions. It is closely connected to executive functions in the prefrontal cortex (Goldstein, 2018). Attention is a cognitive brain mechanism that lets us to pay attention to an external or internal stimulus. Thus, it is crucial to differ passive (involuntary) and active (conscious) attention (Bradesko, 2022). Concentration is the ability to work in a focused manner, or to persist with a stimulus (Mravlje, 1999). Individuals with poor concentration have a slow cognitive pace and information process, and tend to be apathetic (Ling Chang et al, 2021). Regarding the prevalence of concentration problems, they are widespread and closely tied to clinical, mental and environmental factors along with lifestyle ones. According to researches, up to 90% of individuals, suffering from depressive disorder, report concentration issues as root causes (Zuckerbrot et al., 2018). 6,1 million children in USA have been diagnosed with ADHD (CDC, 2023). Recent global studies showcase that around 5-10% of school-aged children suffer from lack of attention during classes, which is resulting in poor academic performance, low self-esteem and particular

behavioral changes (WHO, 2020). All these evidences illustrate that concentration issues are being globally prevalent, which pushes us suggest and implement proper and creative solutions.

Causes of Concentration Problems

The ability to concentrate is considered as the ability to keep focus on a particular task or activity for a certain period of time. This period can be various according to some factors such as age and mental abilities. Studies show that average concentration ability by age are classified by as following:

Children 4-5 years old: around 5-10 minutes;

Children 6-8 years old: around 10-20 minutes;

Children 9-13 years old: around 20-30 minutes (WHO, 2020). There are curtain aspects of concentration that help us to define how well our child is concentrated:

- focusing on the specific assignment;
- listening attentively;
- maintaining focus over time;
- staying quiet;
- following the instructions of the educator;
- following verbal and non-verbal cues;
- ignoring external distractions, such as noises or sounds.

By checking how well these processes are undergoing, educators and parents can identify if there is any issue with a child's attention. However, these parameters are limited at some point, thus, having an idea about symptoms of concentration problems in children can be useful:

- *Being unattentive when spoken to*

One of the most frequent complaints by teachers are the pupils who do not seem to be listening when spoken to! In my experience, I have come across this condition a lot, where majority of pupils do not react the teacher when spoken or asked questions directly. Instead, they are busy with playing minor school supplies such as pens or colorful pencils; drawing abstract pictures on a sheet of paper or looking outside through windows.

- *Inability to sustain a chain of thoughts.*

When asked to tell poems or stories, a number of pupils may forget what they are telling if something interrupts them and It will be difficult for them to remember where the story left off. They may jump over to unrelated parts or stories unconsciously, and when occurs regularly, it can be a sign of a problem with concentration.

- *Need for repeating directions.*

There is a category of pupils who need directions repeated several times. In most cases, they possess high potential of intelligence which can absorb and digest new information quickly, however, due to their lower focus level, teachers often have to repeat instructions to remember .

A number of factors can cause to lower attention span, that I outline them as the following:

1) Too Many Stimuli

Recent researchs have showed that short videos and diversity of contents give constant stimulation to a child's brain. As the length of videos and reels that children watch on their smartphones have been shortened significantly to 1-5 minutes, their brain bring stimuli every 1-2 minutes constantly. As a result of such regular immersion by a digital tool, an individual brain gets used to taking a dophamine from the consumption of visual digital stuff, which makes them feel comfortable and release stress along with worries (Potapova et al, 2021). Such 'quite wake' brain is not engaged in active or cognitive activities that require direct attention, including academic works or puzzles. Studies by

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Potapova showcase that the brain remains inactive and illustrate less productive performance, which results in decreases with concentration and vigorous activity. That is one reason of why most children today can not focus on a task for a longer time.

2) No Interest to a Subject

Sometimes pupils may not have enough interest or motivation to learn the subject, thus it is difficult for them to maintain focus during the class. They may find the subject unrelated to their future goals or unnecessary. They do not see the relevance or any value in their learning, therefore it may lead them to ignore the engagement into learning atmospheres. A lack of incentives may be a crucial factor of student boredom in the classroom. When I teach high school pupils, I see a lot of students who show no interest to the subject. They say about its unimportance for their future career when I asked about the reason of their unattentiveness. The students, who have a desire for choosing a vocational field, consider that learning a foreign language is a waste of time, because they think that being a master in their job is enough for being successful and for being financially independent. At that time, I try to explain the benefits of knowing a foreign language and its impact on improving and enlarging his/her work or business. How foreign languages help to open doors to the world and what opportunities they can gain through it are the topics which I constantly tell my students.

3) Poor Diet or Sleep

If a child is not getting a 8-9 hours of recommended sleep, which keeps the mind calm and relaxed, it may be challenging for him to keep attention during classes. Due to lack of energy for maintaining concentration and poor brain activeness, they tend to be distracted from even minor things such as chatty peers or a cluttered workstation. Balanced diet is another important factor for a child to immerse himself to the learning process. Junk foods and unhealthy diet that has a shortage of vitamins and nutrients may result in decreasing attention span of a child or causing another health issues. Therefore, it is crucial for every child to get proper nutrition and rest.

4) Personal Problems

Unhealthy and troubled living atmosphere naturally impact the academic performance of a child. He finds focusing on his regular activities difficult due to anxious or no peaceful mind. His mind will be unconsciously busy with chaotic home problems and conditions, which pushes him to live in another planet during the class.

5) Learner Diagnosed with ADD and ADHD

Attention Deficit Disorder (ADD) and Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) may be the reason of persistent inattention. These disorders can be observed through constant symptoms of impulsively, along with hyperactivity. Sometimes these conditions can be challenging to identify solely by a mental health issues or poor child development such as conducting problems or speech or extreme mood swings. In most cases, children with these disorders often stay undiagnosed, because they may be given labels as disobedient or rebellious, which can influence negatively in classroom engagement and building relationships with other classmates. Recent studies conducted in Anna Freud Mental Health Schools identified a number of signs of ADD and ADHD:

- impulsive behavior (doing things unconsciously)
- struggling to sit still
- difficulties in communicating
- constant interrupts others
- challenges in concentrating

- not following the instructions or directions
- difficulties in organizing themselves and their school tasks properly
- shortages in memorization

The sooner and earlier a child is diagnosed, the easier they can get proper recovery and support.

6) Mental Health Concerns

The prevalence of mental health concerning conditions among students has become a noticeable factor to impact their immersion into learning atmospheres and overall well-being in recent times. Students are grappling with these kinds of challenges such as anxiety, depression, isolation or stress, which can undoubtedly affect to undermining their focus, activeness and energy to continue their studies. One of the reasons may be an anxiety of failing from exams, showing poor academic performance. Therefore, educators must be attentive to observe their learners and create a safer and more supportive learning environments where learners can express themselves without fears and feel comfortably in sharing their concerns and feelings.

7) Mismatched Learning Style

Learning styles are different: some pupils learn by watching visual materials, while others do by listening or touching. If an educator conducts a class by mismatched teaching styles, a child may lose interest or concentration to understand the subject matter.

Each of these issues can be solved with the cooperation of a teacher and parents, along with well-organized classroom setting and plans.

Creative Solutions and Approaches

Understanding why students aren't maintaining their focus for longer periods and not pushing themselves to learn classroom materials is the first step toward address concentration problems. Incorporating multifaceted approaches and creative solutions are required from educator to engage bored students into learning processes. By applying innovative teaching techniques and promoting a sense of relevance and goals, educators can reignite learners' passion and enthusiasm for the classroom. The following are a number of solutions that experts have recommended and additional approaches from my teaching experience:

1. Choosing age and level-based activities

I took this solution from my experience, because in my early years as a teacher, I would use more difficult materials for middle class pupils and when they had difficulty in doing them, I used to think them as less intelligent and lazier ones. As I had less experience and knowledge in teaching as well as less methodology skills, I applied wrong teaching approaches in my language teaching classes. Later on, by participating in various teacher trainings, learning from other colleagues, I understood my wrongdoings and corrected them. Now I have a habit of defining the age and level of my learners from the first class by taking level placement tests. This helps me a lot in choosing right materials and methods for my pupils. In appendix 1, I attached one of the placement tests that I use in my teaching as a sample.

2. Combining Various Types of Activities

Diversity in activities is very crucial to keeping learners focused to the class, which increase their interest and comprehension. My strategy is starting the class from easier activities and gradually increase difficulty level so as to encourage self-confidence in them and maintain interest over longer time. I try to use at least two types of activities in each class including skills incorporated and oral training. For instance, now in 7 grade pupils' reading class, I put the recorded version of a text to teach correct pronunciation to pupils and I push them to read it one by one from at least two

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sentences then retell it, which improves their speaking and pronunciation. I can define their understanding of the material by doing questionnaires and checking their post-reading activities.

3. Games for Better Concentration

Didactic games designed to develop comprehension and sustain concentration not only help teachers to entertain children, but also foster their cognitive abilities and analytical skills. Games should provide possibilities for reflectivity exploring phenomena, testing hypothesis and constructing objects (Kiili, 2004). These games provide chances for learners to stimulate their memory, logical thinking and the ability to think outside the box. A research by University of Maribor showcases that didactic games serve to practise observations and improve speech quality and fluency. There are numerous didactic games which enrich the diversity and content of lessons such as riddles, puzzles, illustrations, dictation and tongue twisters.

4. Using Digital Tools

In recent years, numerous innovative digital tools have been applied into teaching processes to increase the quality and efficiency of it. Generally, the primary goal of educational tools is to supply learners with challenges related to the task. Via smartboards and computers, educators can use different teaching platforms and technologies to put more colors into their classes. The most used tools in my classes are Wordwall, Duolingo, ClassDojo, Kahoot, Jeopardy, Lingoda, and Storybird. All these offer interactive whiteboards with features that is designed for language teaching as well as personalized learning practises. I mostly utilize these websites in revision classes after completing all activities in the textbook. My students love these activities, because they are fun, engaging and compelling. I often use competitive educational games in Wordwall, dividing the class into small groups. In these competitions, even weaker students activity participate and contribute to the winning of their groups. Sounds, designs and diverse thematic questions help me to wake up all bored minds. Appendix 2 illustrates samples of my classes where I use digital teaching approaches. CommonLit helps me to find proper reading materials with tools to analysis and comprehension. With the help of Storybird, I can encourage my students to use visual prompts and story building features which are designed for fostering creative writing skills.

5. Using Sound in the Classroom

Sounds hold a huge influence role in how individuals interact with the environment. Music has the ability to stimulate human emotions and feelings, therefore using it properly in language teaching classes can positively impact the increased motivation, brain activeness and providing lively learning atmosphere for students. Some are being used during classes as therapy to reduce stress, anxiety and stimulate relaxation, which enables learners to keep their concentration. According to the research by Mayer (2002), it became clear that individuals learn better from visuals and audio rather than from visual only. Another research conducted by Azmi (2023) reveals that learning obstacles can be overcome or reduced by utilizing the right sort of music, which is specifically created for stimuli the human cognitive skills to enhance their motivation and concentration. In my teaching, I like using calm music in the background in writing classes. It helps learners to relax and focus on their work, calming their brain.

6. Mindfulness and SEL classes

Mindfulness and Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) classes are powerful and practical tools for fostering student concentration. Educators can facilitate learners with essential cognitive and psychological implications not only for academic success, but also for maintaining concentration, promoting overall well-being in a dynamic world full of distractions. These classes contribute to

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improve the quality of learning by teaching the recognition of distractions, regulate attention, effective ways of managing stress and anxiety, developing self-management and responsible decision-making skills. Baime (2011) outlines that mindfulness training specifically targets focus control, by showing individuals the awareness of their attention lapses and return it. Lutz (2008) found that meditation practises combined with mindfulness can lead to improvements in brain activity connected with attention and cognitive control. This reduces emotional 'swings' that can associate with focus. Other researchers highlight that mindfulness training help to enhance memory capacity that is closely interfered with concentration. Baime (2010) suggested the viewpoint that mindfulness meditation training help to reduce mind-wandering in demanding academic performance.

Conclusion

Concentration problems in students are a complex and multifaceted issue that demands a more comprehensive measurements. Observing learners, and analyzing their learning processes are useful steps for teachers to keep them engaged into classes. By understanding different types of concentration issues and implementing creative solutions, teachers can lead pupils to enhance their focus, promote their learning experiences, and create a supportive environment which supports academic success.

Appendix 1.

PLACEMENT TEST

Underline the correct answer, a), b), c) or d).

1 I _____ a student of English.

- a) are b) is
c) *am* d) aren't

2 She's from Tokyo. She _____ Japanese.

- a) is from b) is
c) isn't d) are from

3 _____'s your first name?

- a) Who b) What
c) How d) Where

4 I love music but I _____ like TV.

- a) do b) does
c) doesn't d) don't

5 When _____ have lunch?

- a) is he b) he's
c) do he d) does he

6 They start _____ school at 8.00 in the morning.

- a) to b) at
c) --- d) the

7 She's very friendly but she _____ very quiet.

- a) never is b)'s often
c) often is d) never

8 How many children _____ got?

- a) they've b) have they
c) they d) do they

9 _____ a sofa and two armchairs in the living room.

- a) It's b) There's
c) There have d) There are

10 The cinema is _____ the bank.

- a) next b) in front
c) opposite d) under

11 You _____ buy shoes in a post office.

- a) can to b) can't
c) can d) are

12 Is there _____ butter in the fridge?

- a) one b) some
c) any d) an

13 We _____ born in 1985.

- a) is b) were
c) was d) did

14 They _____ to France when they were six.

- a) moves b) moved
c) move d) moving

15 They went for a picnic with some friends _____ Sunday.

- a) at b) the
c) on d) in

16 _____ they do a lot of sport when they were at school?

- a) Were b) Is
c) Was d) Did

17 He stayed at the _____ hotel in town.

- a) more expensive b) expensivest
c) expensive d) most expensive

18 They _____ their homework now.

- a) are do b) did
c) are doing d) does

19 What _____ your sister look like?

- a) is b) do
c) are d) does

Appendix 2

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